

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCES OF USER EXPERIENCE AND USER INTERFACE DESIGN

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Government agencies provide vital information and services that affect people's daily lives. The role of user experience design in IT systems and digital products is undeniable, both in security agencies and ministries, in order to accurately respond to the needs of their citizens, to work as quickly and efficiently as possible.

Information Technologies are developing very quickly and dynamically. The creation and development of new technological possibilities and the maturing of the possibilities of integration of systems make a practical contribution to society and play a major role in the development of society. Currently, it is impossible to imagine the work of any enterprise without information technologies.

The purpose of the article is related to the new and relevant "User Experience (UX)" and "User Interface (UI)" design in today's IT sphere, their common and different aspects. Especially in the process of developing and applying digital products, the important role of these areas is undeniable. Although neither term is new, it is very common for people in digital product design to use these terms interchangeably or sometimes incorrectly. A user interface is a place where interactions between humans and machines take place. It allows users to effectively control a machine to perform a task or achieve a specific goal, such as making a purchase or downloading an application [4]. User interfaces consist of input hardware (devices that control the machine, such as a keyboard, mouse, or joystick) and output equipment (devices that provide information to users, such as monitors, audio equipment, or printers). Input devices work together with output devices so that users can fully control the machine [5, p.35].

There are many different user interfaces. The three most common user interfaces are the command-line interface, the graphical user interface, and the voice-activated user interface [2, p86].

Command line interface. Interactions were linear - the user (operator) typed a command, and the machine responded to the command either using printed output or displaying a message on the monitor [4]. Since users had to know machine language to interact with computers, the complexity of such interaction was quite high.

Graphical user interface. A graphical user interface (GUI) is a form of user interface that allows users to interact with digital products through visual elements. When users interact with a GUI, they move through a series of pages or screens. These pages/screens contain static elements (such as text sections) and active elements (such as buttons and other interactive controls) [1, p102]. GUI is the most common type of UI for digital products. The popularization of GUI interfaces also created a demand for people who

will design products for these interfaces - UI designers. Today, the spectrum of responsibilities for UI designers has increased significantly. Mobile devices, VR headsets, and Automotive HMIs all have a GUI interface [3, p64].

Voice-based interfaces. "The best interface is not an interface" is a famous quote from Golden Krishna's book *The Simple Path to Brilliant Technology*. The learning curve is a big problem with the GUI interface. Every time users interact with a new product that has a GUI, they need to spend some time learning how to use it. In general, the longer users spend learning how to use a particular product, the higher the learning curve. For a long time, people in the design industry dreamed of getting a zero user interface [3, p.165; 5, p. 45].

The closest we come to a zero UI level are voice user interfaces, which allow the user's voice to interact with the system. Recent advances in natural language processing have made it possible to design intelligent AI-powered systems such as Amazon Alexa.[4]

Key features of a well-designed user interface. No matter what interface you develop, you should always check that it has the following features:

- Clarity, as a visual metaphor, all elements of the user interface are open to users. Users should not need to decipher the meaning of a particular element.
- Familiar UI allows your users to draw on their previous experiences when they interact with your product.
- Keeping your interface consistent throughout your product allows users to recognize usage patterns.
- Forgiveness: a good user interface forgives users for their mistakes.
- Efficiency: A good user interface allows users to provide minimal input to achieve desired results. It also provides shortcuts to make interactions more productive for experienced users [1, p.423].

Interface design methods. The main interface design techniques are prototyping and simulation. UI designers create a prototype based on the requirements they derive from ideation sessions and interaction specifications. Simulation is part of validating design decisions by testing a prototype with people who represent the target audience. It is an important part of usability testing sessions. When conducting usability testing, the product team gives testers a prototype and a set of pre-defined tasks and sees what problems they encounter during interaction [4].

User-centered design. User-Centered Design is an interactive step that places the end user at the center of the product's planning, design, and development phases to identify all of the customer's needs and create a successful user experience. In other words, it is the method

or process by which we can create a good user experience. Some key principles of the UCSD process are:

- User focus
- Active user participation
- Systems development should be both iterative and incremental
- Simple design representations
- Prototyping

The idea behind this methodology is that designers and developers will increase their chances of identifying usability problems in time to do something about them, thereby increasing their chances of creating usable software [2, p. 302].

User experience design. User Experience design is a broad term that encompasses both traditional human-computer interaction (HCI) design and all aspects of a product or service as perceived by users. However, it is mainly used in the digital domain. User Experience, like UCD, refers to human-first design. Rooted in psychology and conscious behavior, this design method focuses on understanding user behavior by considering the user's feelings, frustrations, and reactions while using the product. It aims to create simple, seamless and efficient interactions for users, while providing meaningful experiences [3, p. 225].

It took a long time for the design community to settle on the term "UX". Over the years, there have been creative job titles like "Experience Designers" and "Interaction Architects," but ultimately the roles behind these titles have the same goal: To improve customer-product relationships using in-depth research, user behavior analysis, and creative design solutions. UX design centers [4]:

- Understanding the user
- Show a logical journey for the user
- Providing optimal functionality for the user
- Implementation and testing

UI and UX design relationship. In the tech world, we're used to seeing these two roles listed together either as a hybrid role in recruiting or in the same bullet point in a job description. Broadly speaking, and as I've discussed, there's a lot of overlap between the two disciplines that contributes to this. As a result, they serve to create a successful product that interests users and satisfies their needs. These are design practices that share many of the same goals, objectives, and mindsets. At a high level, the combination of a hybrid role seems only logical [5, p.338].

The combination of UX and UI roles can be considered similar to someone who is responsible for both front-end and back-end work. Although both ends of development involve coding, the tools, concerns, and approaches often differ. Organizations can choose to hire such hybrid or specialized roles based on their needs, workloads and resources.

The role of the UX designer. Recently, many companies have realized that good design is a competitive advantage and are willing to invest significant resources in creating a great user experience. As a result, the role of UX designer has emerged and is in high demand [4].

Simply put, UX design is a human-first approach to product design. UX designers are responsible for analyzing the needs of the target audience and ensuring that the company creates products that meet those needs. UX design is a multidisciplinary field in which UX designers can participate in various areas of product development, such as product research, ideation, prototyping, testing [1, p78].

Duties of a UX designer include:

- Understanding users. UX design usually begins with extensive research aimed at understanding the target audience, their wants and needs. Empathy is a crucial skill for UX designers. It helps UX designers understand and uncover the needs and emotions of the people they are designing for.

- Create a design strategy. Design strategy involves understanding a product's purpose, mapping out a logical journey.

- Analysis of interaction design. UX designers analyze how people use products—their interaction habits, personal preferences, and the shortcuts they take when interacting with the UI. All ideas are used in proposing better design solutions.

- Creation of sketches and prototypes. UX designers need to create sketches or prototypes to quickly design and present their ideas. UX designers are constantly involved in the execution of a product. They interact with all team members to ensure product design is moving in the right direction [4].

The role of the UI designer. The role of UI designers is more related to the visual presentation of information. UI designers must have graphic design, visual design, and branding skills to create good looking and responsive interfaces. Generally, UI designers take the user flow and sketches for individual screens/pages created by UX designers (the design skeleton) and turn it into an aesthetically pleasing example [4].

Being a good designer means several things, such as:

- Attention to detail. Good designers know that "the devil is in the detail" and constantly improve the small elements of their solutions.

- Good problem solving skills. Whatever you do in design, you are always solving a specific problem. Designers must be willing to spend enough time to find a suitable solution.

Also, there are a few specific skills that a UI designer should know:

- Competitive analysis. Be able to analyze and conduct competitive analysis of products and their visual design decisions.

- Responsive design. Ensure UI design looks great on any screen size and resolution.

- Communication. Generally, a UI designer works closely with UX designers and engineering staff. Communication skills required to understand technical feasibility. The future of UX/UI design. It goes without saying that the technology sector is competitive. Being first in the market can give a start-up an advantage, but compared to competitors, it is effective design that determines success [3, p125].

Looking to the future, it is clearly reasonable to expect an increased demand for custom UI and UX professionals. As organizations realize the importance of these roles, there will be plenty of work for future designers.

References:

1. Allen, J. and Chudley, J., 2012. Smashing UX Design: Foundations for Designing Online User Experiences” Excerpt From: Jesmond Allen and James Chudley. “Smashing UX Design: Foundations for Designing Online User Experiences. p. 746.
2. Fowler, S. and Stanwick, V., 2004. WEB APPLICATION DESIGN HANDBOOK Best Practices for Web-Based Software. p. 689.

3. Gilbert, R., 2019. Inclusive Design for a Digital World, Designing with Accessibility in Mind. p. 291.

4. Ideas. 2021. UI vs. UX Design: The Similarities & Differences | Adobe XD Ideas. [online] Available at: <<https://xd.adobe.com/ideas/process/ui-design/ui-vs-ux-design-understanding-similarities-and-differences/>>.

5. Krug, S., 2006. Don't Make Me Think! A Common Sense Approach to Web Usability. 2nd ed. p. 397.